

THE NOTION OF THE CONCEPT “MOTHER” IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a linguistic and cultural comparison and analysis of the peculiarities of proverbs on the concept of “mother” in English and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: concept, cognitive, linguaculturology, anthropocentric, cognitology, cultural image.

INTRODUCTION

In the 20th century, collection of anthropocentric, functional, cognitive and dynamic paradigms occupied the position of structural paradigm. Movement of interests of researcher from the object of cognition to the subject in anthropocentric paradigm, it can be understood the analysis of language in human being and human being in language. It caused to the appearance of new branch of linguistics called “cognitive linguistics or cognitology”. Cognitive linguistics plays an important role in revealing specific features of the languages from the anthropocentric point of view. The term concept is considered the main part of cognitology. It was introduced to the linguistics in the middle of the 20th century and first used in S. A. Askoldov’s article under the title “Concept and word” and she defined this term as a mental formation that replaces an indefinite number of objects of the same kind in the process of thought.¹²

The authors of the “Brief Dictionary of Cognitive Terms” - E.S. Kubryakova, V.Z. Demyankov, Yu.G. Pankratz and L.G. Luzin - they interpret the notion of a concept from a slightly different point of view. They consider concepts as ideal abstract units, the meanings that a person operates in the processes of thinking, reflecting the content of experience and knowledge, the content of the results of all human activities and the processes of knowing the world around them in the form of certain units, “knowledge quanta”. The content of the concept includes information about what the individual knows, assumes, thinks, imagines about a particular fragment of the world. Concepts reduce the whole variety of observed phenomena to something unified, for specific categories and classes developed by society.

And they can be expressed by words, word combinations, sayings, proverbs and etc. According to the paremiologist Wolfgang Mieder “A proverb is a short, generally known sentence of the folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a

¹² Приходько А. Н. Концепты и концептосистемы / А. Н. Приходько. – Днепропетровск: Белая Е. А., 2013. – 307 с.

metaphorical, fixed and memorable form and which is handed down from generation to generation".¹³ In this article, common and specific features of the concept "mother" will be analyzed with the help of Uzbek and English proverbs.

MAIN PART

This article discusses cognitive and linguoculturologic analysis of the concept of "mother" and the comparison of proverbs in English language. The proverbs are the spiritual richness and cultural heritage of the people for many years. Proverbs are a kind of legends. When analyzing family and family traditions and teaching methods in English and a number of languages, it is well known that the notion of mother is important in all languages. It is considered as a universal concept.

1) Mother is valued for everyone.

In Uzbek: "Ona-olam faxridir", "Bola ham ona deydi, ona ham ona deydi", "Ona bilan bola-gul bilan lola" ("Mother is proud", "The child calls a mother, mother calls her mother", "Mother and child, flower and tulip").¹⁴

In English: "Paradise is under the feet of mothers", "She hath a mark after her mother".

2) It is also a symbol of peace and tranquility in the linguistic tradition of the three languages.

In Uzbek: "Ona hayotning guli, bola uning bulbuli", "Ona oyog'i bilan beshikni, qo'li bilan ro'zg'orni tebratar", ("Mother is a flower of life, child is her nightingale", "Mother cradles with her feet, her mouth grows").

In English: "An ounce of mother wit is worth a pound of learning".

3) It is known in the Uzbek and English legends that each mother values her child and cares for all her.

In Uzbek: "Onaning bolaga olaligi yo'q", "Onangni yaxshiligini bemor bo'lsang bilarsan" ("There is no alien mother for a child", "You know how good your mother when you are ill").

In English: "Praise the child and you make love to the mother", "Every mother thinks her own gosling a swan", "A child may have too much of his mother's blessing".¹⁵

4) In English, many thoughts are found not only on the appearance of the girl but also on her character and behavior.

In Uzbek: "Eshigi yomonning uyiga borma, onasi yomonning qizini olma" "Semiz qo'yning go'shti yaxshi, Oqila onaning qizi" ("Don't go to the house of the bad, do not take the daughter of the bad mother", "The meat of the fat sheep is delicious and the daughter of the wise woman is good").

¹³ Mieder, Wolfgang. 1985. "Popular Views of the Proverb." *Proverbium* 2: 109–143; also in Mieder 1993: 18–40.

¹⁴ Uzbek folklore proverbs. Chief editorial of publishing and printing stock company "Sharq". Tashkent. 2012

¹⁵ Jennifer Speake. *The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs*. The fifth edition. Oxford University Press, 2008- 625.

In English: “Like mother, like daughter”, “Take a vine of a good soil and daughter of a good mother”

5) It is possible to find many proverbs in the linguistic of two languages about respect and value for mother.

In Uzbek, “Onasini suyganning bolasini suy”, “Onangni senda shunchalar ko‘p haqqi borki, sen unga har qancha yaxshilik qilsang ham oz”, “Ona-olam faxridir” (“He is the mother of the one who loves his mother”, “You have a mother so much about you, that you do not do anything good for her”, “Mother is a proud of the world”).

In English: “A man loves his sweetheart the most, his wife the best, but his mother the longest”, “Paradise is under the feet of mothers”.

6) The role of mother in the upbringing of children is crucial.

In Uzbek, “Ona suti bilan kirmagan, tana suti bilan kirmas” “Olmaning tagiga olma tushadi”, “Qush uyasida ko‘rganini qiladi” (“The thing does not come in with mother’s milk, does not enter with the milk of the body”, “An apple falls under the apple”, “A bird do thing which saw in its nest”).

In English: “Like mother, like daughter”, “Good mother, child good”.

MATERIAL METHOD

Cognitive linguistics, or cognitive metaphor theory serves as a means to systematise and form linguistics with regard to concepts of the linguistic world image. The concept of any given word is determined through its semantic and associative field. Words express the information in the semantic and associative fields, and they are regarded as separate elements of cognitive and pragmatic meanings.

A concept is a linguo-philosophical unit that was introduced thanks to an anthropocentric approach in linguistics. A concept defines and groups almost every possible meaning of any given word and their development. Philosopher Anselm (1033-1109) was the first to introduce the term “concept”. In the Latin language it has several meanings: *conseptio* – 1) a connection, code, system; 2) warehouse; 3) signing legal acts; 4) seeds receiving; 5) a sentence [16]. The dichotomy of language and thinking has been considered in the Russian linguistics. It is widely believed that the following scientists laid the theoretical foundation of the term “concept”: E.F. Karsky, A.A. Shakhmatov, A.A. Potebnja, A.N. Afanasiev, V.N. Teliya, A.N. Sobolevsky, D.S. Likhachov, V.V. Vorobiev, V.A. Maslova, N.D. Arutyunova, E.S. Kubryakova, A.N. Morokovsky, N.K. Ryabtseva, V. Airapetyan, V.V. Kolesov, A.Ya. Gurevich, A. Wierzbicka, M. Minsky, etc. The term “concept” has many definitions and representations. Professor V.A. Maslova analysed various definitions and provided her own variant: “A concept is a semantic unit that has linguo-cultural features and characterises speakers of any chosen ethnoculture. While

reflecting an ethnic mindset, a concept marks the ethnic language world image and serves as the so-called brick to build “the house of our being”

CONCLUSION

The results of the linguistic analysis of proverbs in Uzbek and English indicate that in both languages, one can find similarities. In conclusion, it is important to note that the mother is priceless for every human being and her mother is ready for everything for her children.

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